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ABSTRACTS

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AI-Based System for Real-Time Monitoring of Water Quality in context of the Indian Urban Water Landscape

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Abstract: Water quality monitoring is a crucial requirement for both environment and healthcare management. The growing challenges faced by India's diverse water bodies, demand more efficient real time monitoring systems that enable proactive interventions and actionable insights. To address these need, the present work introduces an AI-driven system aimed towards significant improvement in water quality monitoring, offering real-time insights, adaptive learning and predictive capabilities. The proposed system comprises of a network of sensors to be strategically placed across different water sources and collect real time data on key indicators such as pH, dissolved oxygen, contaminants, turbidity, nutrient levels etc. These data points are transmitted to an in-house central AI-powered platform enabled with sophisticated machine learning models to identify anomalies. The derived insights will be disseminated to facilitating decision-making with actionable recommendations for water management and benefiting stakeholders. The system also aligns with the government's initiatives for a "Digital India" by leveraging technology to enhance environmental monitoring and safeguard water resources. Thus by harnessing the power of artificial intelligence, remote sensing technologies and IoT devices the proposedintegrated system has the potential to enhance water quality management, ensuring the availability of clean and safe urban water. As a case study, a GP model utilizing a dataset of 3276 values for critical water quality parameters has been built and the preliminary results will be presented during the conference.

Keywords: AI, adaptive learning, environment monitoring, IoT, remote sensing, real-time, machine learning water quality monitoring, sensor.

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